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Osteoarthritis Course Peculiarities Combined with Obesity, Arterial Hypertension, and Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

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***Abstract:** Osteoarthritis is a degenerative joint disease. It causes pain, swelling, and stiffness, affecting a person's ability to move freely. Osteoarthritis affects the entire joint, including the tissues around it. It is most common in the knees, hips, spine, and hands. Many factors can contribute to the development of osteoarthritis. Some include a history of joint injury or overuse, older age, and being overweight. It affects women more than men. Exercise and healthy eating to build strong muscles and maintain a healthy weight can reduce symptoms. In severe cases, joint replacement surgery is used to reduce pain and restore mobility.*

***Key words:** osteoarthritis; type 2 diabetes; obesity; arterial hypertension; oxidative stress; antioxidant defense system; cytokines; matrilin 3.*

Introduction.

Symptoms of osteoarthritis include pain, swelling, stiffness, and difficulty moving the affected joint. As a consequence of reduced movement, muscles often lose strength and people become less able to perform physical activities. Osteoarthritis can affect any joint, but is most common in the knees, hips, spine, and small joints in the hands. Muscles and tissue around the joint are often affected. Symptoms can develop slowly or start quickly after an injury or strain. Osteoarthritis is chronic and often progressive, so changes occur gradually over time. In severe cases, it can make the joint unusable and cause long-term pain. Some people feel pain even when they are resting. Being less physically active can lead to other conditions, such as cardiovascular disease, obesity, and diabetes. Osteoarthritis can greatly reduce quality of life. It makes movement painful and difficult, which can stop people from participating in home, work, or social activities. This can lead to mental health impacts, trouble sleeping, and problems in relationships.

The objective of the study is to examine the clinical indices of articular syndrome in patients with OA combined with type 2 diabetes mellitus, obesity, and arterial hypertension and their effect on the body

Study methods and materials. The study involved 116 patients and the following clinical groups of case follow-up were distinguished: group – 37 patients with OA; II group – 21 patients with combined with arterial hypertension; III group – 41 patients with concomitant arterial hypertension and abdominal obesity; V group – 17 patients with combined with arterial hypertension, abdominal obesity, and type 2 diabetes mellitus; V pya - 25 practically healthy people.

The results of the study. It was established that in the I group patients with mild OA prevailed; the association of arterial hypertension caused a percentage increase in patients with severe OA in the II group. However, an extremely severe course of OA 58,9% was found in patients of the IV group. The increase in body weight has led to an increase in the percentage of patients with very severe and extremely severe OA. An increase in the intensity of arthrological pain, in particular night pain, abnormal mobility with a significant disturbance of daily activities was characteristic for patients with OA, AH, abdominal obesity with the joining of type 2 DM.

Conclusion. The combined course of OA, AH, obesity and type 2 DM is accompanied by an increase in the intensity of joint pain, a disturbance in motor function and the daily activities of patients.

The treatment of osteoarthritis often involves different health workers, who contribute to a rehabilitative strategy tailored to the needs and preferences of the person.

Self-care is an important part of the management of osteoarthritis. Education and support can help people learn to cope with the physical and mental effects of osteoarthritis. People with osteoarthritis should speak to a healthcare worker to build a personalized care plan. Staying active and maintaining a healthy weight can help reduce symptoms and the risk of their progression.

Early diagnosis and follow-up of a treatment plan are the best way to slow the disease and optimize function.

Exercise can strengthen the affected muscles and help mobility. Other therapeutic approaches can help the joint move properly and allow people to continue their daily activities. Braces and other assistive technologies can help people remain independent when movement becomes more difficult. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) can be prescribed to control pain. Joint replacement surgery can reduce pain, restore movement, and improve quality of life for most people with severely affected joints. These surgeries are most commonly performed on the hip and knee. It is important to maintain a healthy weight. Education and counseling are important to help people manage their symptoms and work-related tasks.